

Equity in international research

Key principles of equitable research collaboration for research teams:

We define equitable collaborations as ‘Mutually advantageous partnerships built on trust, where all partners are intellectual contributors to the project who work together to ensure that tasks and rewards are shared in a fair manner that addresses inequalities’.

These guidelines aim to support Sanger research teams to build and manage equitable partnerships with partners based in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). They are not a rigid checklist of instructions and should not be imposed on partners. Rather, they should serve as a suggested starting point towards a strategy for equitable collaboration that is co-developed with partners on a case-by-case basis.

Please see the full report for more detailed guidelines, case studies, context on power asymmetries, the stakeholder engagement process, and further resources.

These guidelines focus on embedding equity in collaborations between research teams and institutes. However, equitable engagement with non-academic stakeholders such as local communities is also highly important, and we encourage Sanger research teams to explore external resources and expertise if this is necessary. Please see the full report for suggested resources.

1. ESTABLISH A TRUST-BASED PARTNERSHIP

1A

Identify potential collaborators using a variety of means, such as encouraging research teams to approach you with ideas, leveraging networks, or building on previous relationships.

1B

Prioritise building trust with potential partners through transparency, receptive communication and by emphasising your personal commitment to research equity.

1C

Before entering into a formal collaboration, jointly agree a research agenda and co-develop equity-oriented research strategies with potential partners, ideally through in-person meetings.

2. FORMALISE THE COLLABORATION

2A

Submit a joint research proposal that allocates funding equitably and includes capacity building.

2B

Before formal legal negotiation, agree important high-level components with research partners. Afterwards, follow-up to ensure contracts are mutually beneficial.

2C

Create simple-language non-legal 'guiding principles of partnership' with all partners, including junior researchers.

3. CONDUCT JOINT RESEARCH

3A

Build in regular meetings with partners to exchange updates on research progress and develop inclusive strategies for overcoming obstacles.

3B

Regularly evaluate progress towards equity-oriented goals, whilst establishing and maintaining routes for concerns to be raised.

3C

Foster an inclusive working environment where all partners are encouraged to voice ideas, priorities and concerns, and linguistic and cultural diversity is celebrated.

4. SHARE AND BUILD RESEARCH CAPACITY

4A

Develop sustainable and holistic ways to share skills and knowledge, support professional development, and create efficiencies in the research process.

4B

Work with partners to identify and overcome limitations in institutional and infrastructural capacity.

4C

Adapt roles and responsibilities throughout the research process to allow partners to take advantage of strengthened research capacity.

5. SHARE OUTPUTS AND RECOGNITION

5A

Share recognition and reward with all partners, including publication authorship, external presentation opportunities, and shares of revenue and other benefits from commercialisation of intellectual property.

5B

Securely share data between partners throughout the project life cycle if possible, and ensure open (or managed) access to data and publications externally whilst addressing fears of scooping.

5C

Continue sustainable relationships with partners after the project has finished by keeping in touch and actively seeking further collaboration opportunities.